

Elements of the Theory of Cycle of Money without Enforcement Savings

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to show the negative impact on the economy of having low enforcement savings. Booster savings are those that have a positive effect on an economy as opposed to escape savings. This analysis has used the Q.E. (Quantification of Everything) method and its econometric approach. Also, it uses the E.Q.E. (Econometric Quantification of Everything) method. The results confirm the initial hypothesis that booster savings show the amount of money available in an economy, as they allow money to be reused and better dispersed, resulting in greater consumption and investment. If money is concentrated in companies that substitute smaller domestic companies, then their super profits are impossible to consume and are usually stored in tax havens and international banks, with the result that this amount of money is lost from the economy.

INTRODUCTION

One basic problem in the current study of economics is that savings are considered as a single type in the consequences of the economy. By single type, I mean that the savings should be distinguished in two cases, at least. This allows the study of their impact on the economy in an accurate way. Savings have not always positive impact on the economy. Savings could have a negative impact on the economy when they are about the escape savings. On the other hand, savings could have a positive impact on the economy when they are enforcement savings. In that way, it is plausible to transform the science of Economics into Economic Engineering. The reason for this is that the economic elements when distinguished with a positive and negative impact could be controlled in multiple ways, as the Theory of CM (Cycle of Money) describes.

Moreover, the current literature review studies the deficit but not the amount of money that is lost from the economy. For the consideration of the deficit is taken into account the expenditures and the revenue. The theory of CM, is about the quantity of money that is in the economy, thinking that that the cycle of money is increased when the enforcement savings are higher than the escaped savings. The deficit is about the expenditures and revenues of the government, but the CM hinges on the main core of the functionality of the economy, and this is the money in the economy. The money as the CM describes shows the condition of the structure of the economy.

A deficit arises when general government expenditure exceeds total revenue, whereas otherwise, it results in a surplus. A deficit can be classified as structural when expenditure is much larger than revenue, and cyclical when economic activity is reduced and therefore revenue is less than expenditure. The most common way to cover the deficit is government borrowing, which, as mentioned earlier, involves paying interest to the country from which it borrows. At this point, it is useful to clarify the concept of primary deficit and primary surplus. A primary deficit is the state budget deficit if interest on public debt is deducted. A primary surplus in an economy exists when government revenues exceed government spending. In case the primary surplus is less than the amount of interest payments, the result is a government deficit, as the revenues are not enough to pay public expenditure and interest. The deficit is usually given as a percentage of GDP to compare it with that of other countries and the country itself in different periods. The Stability and Growth Pact sets limits on government deficits to ensure sound and sustainable public finances. A deficit of more than 3% of GDP is considered excessive and requires corrective measures.

As in the case of a deficit, the same happens with the government debt. I mean that the debt is a subcase of the cycle of money, as the debt is the case where the government can't cover it is expenditures. The reason for this is the case that there is a low cycle of money, showing that the structure and the functionality of this economy are not in an appropriate condition. When the money is lost from the economy the government needs to borrow money, because there is not enough money to tax, as the big companies save their money in tax heavens and external banking systems, because they see their

profit and the optimum financial case for them. Also, big companies which substitute the smaller companies can't consume or invest their super-profits destroying in that way the local economy in a general way, in its function and its structure.

Government debt is the total outstanding debt of the public sector of the economy. The borrowing can be external and internal. Correspondingly, in the first case, there is the external public debt, while in the second case the internal public debt, where all of them ultimately give the total public debt. Public debt is created when a state borrows. It increases when there is a deficit because to cover the difference between income and expenditure, the state will have to borrow. One way to limit debt growth is to create a primary surplus that must be at least equal to interest on servicing public debt. Moreover, the reduction of public debt can be achieved by reducing spending, raising taxes, privatizations, and even declaring bankruptcy according to which the state declares inability to pay its debt. Here it would be useful to mention the term debt restructuring. By debt restructuring, we mean that a country that cannot pay the amortization can make changes to its borrowing terms (e.g. interest rate) and debt structure (e.g. debt charges, capital transactions) (Παπακωνσταντινίου et al., 2013).

Public expenditure belongs to the category of expenditure in the state budget and is made by the various public bodies. Public expenditure in many countries is showing an increasing trend, mainly because of the role played by the State and is one of its main means of action. Their contribution is important and lies in the economic development of a country through, for example, investment, stimulating demand, employment, and income growth in times of recession through, employment programs for the unemployed. Of course, all parameters in an economy should be examined and studied so that their use is for the benefit of society before the government draws up the state budget. Let us consider at this point the categories of public spending in terms of how they affect income and production. First of all, there is expenditure on goods and services. This category includes expenses that constitute the remuneration of a productive factor for its contribution to the production process. Such expenditure is expenditure on construction works, salaries of civil servants, expenditure on education, rents on buildings, expenditure on equipment, etc. In the case, for example, of employees' salaries, salaries constitute remuneration for their contribution to education. In this case, two subcategories can be distinguished. The first subindent is current government expenditure or consumption expenditure, including expenditure on the purchase of consumer goods, i.e. goods covering current needs, e.g. salaries of officials, expenditure on the use of cars owned by Members of Parliament and police officers, rent, etc. The second subindent is public investment expenditure which includes expenditure incurred on the purchase of capital goods, i.e. goods covering long-term needs.

Examples of public investment expenditure are expenditure on the construction of infrastructure projects, actions to support private investment and entrepreneurship, and procurement of equipment and machinery. Secondly, transfer payments, pensions, unemployment benefits, family

allowances, etc. belong to the category of transfer payments. In contrast to the previous category, transfer payments are not the remuneration of factors of production for their contribution to the production process but financial support to groups of people who for some reason are needed (e.g. war invalids, unemployed). Also, this category of public expenditure can be distinguished based on the purpose it is made. So there are income transfers intended to boost household income, e.g. unemployment benefits, and capital transfers where the purpose is to strengthen the capital of enterprises, e.g. subsidies for environmental equipment of companies.

Another part of the state budget is public revenue, which covers public expenditure. In this case, taxes (indirect, income tax) are analyzed, as well as other non-tax sources of income such as income from borrowing and doing business.

A country's main source of revenue is taxes. The tax is a forced unilateral provision of tax units to the state without any *quid pro quo*. The main reason for imposing taxes is to cover the cash needs of a state. In some cases, there may be other reasons for imposing taxes, for example where the state imposes a tax on an activity harmful to the environment to reduce its size. Usually, more than one tax is levied to better meet the goals of the state. Indirect taxes or expenditure taxes are based on taxpayers' expenditures. They are called indirect because they do not burden consumers directly but are imposed on the companies that produce the various products. The burden hits both sides, as businesses pay the tax to the state and then pass the tax on to consumers with increases in the prices of their products. Examples of indirect taxes are value-added tax (VAT) levied on various products, cigarettes, beverages, excise duty on petrol, car registration taxes, etc. Income tax or direct tax is based on the income of taxpayers who are either natural persons or legal entities (corporations). Various sources of income are taken into account for the determination of income, e.g. income from salaried services, real estate, liberal professions, and any discounts and exemptions.

Another important source of government revenue is borrowing. In cases where certain categories of expenditure are not covered by taxation, the state resorts to borrowing. Loans usually have a positive effect when, for example, they are used for investments that help a country's economic development. Loans depending on their maturity can be short-term if they mature in one year, medium-term when they mature in ten years, and long-term when their maturity exceeds ten years. Public loans are divided into loans from abroad when the country borrows from abroad, and loans from within, when resources come from within. In a foreign loan, the borrowing country pays interest to the country from which it borrowed, which has the effect of burdening the economy. This is not the case for domestic loans, where interest accrues to private entities. The money that the government raises from domestic borrowing can come either from private savings by issuing a bond loan, from commercial banks, or from the central bank (Παπακωνσταντινίου et al., 2013).

It follows from the above that both taxation and borrowing have a negative effect on the economy, since they create burdens for economic units, as

shown by CM. In other words, what happens is they reduce the amount of money available either in the short or long term, as the case may be. This means that a vicious circle is created in the economy, which destroys its structure and functioning. The more powerful the money cycle, the less need there is for borrowing and taxation (Challoumis, 2018a, 2019, 2020b, 2021c, 2021f, 2021a, 2021e, 2021b, 2021g).

LITERATURE REVIEW

This paper is about the case of the cycle of money without enforcement savings. The enforcement savings according to the theory of the Cycle of Money (CM) are the savings that return to the economic system. There are escape savings which are the savings that do not return to the economy (Berg et al., 2020; Corti et al., 2020; Rajagopal et al., 2018; Rumayya et al., 2020; Syukur, 2020; Zamudio & Cama, 2020). Therefore, the distinction between booster (enforcement) and evasive (escape) savings is something supported by CM's innovation, as the existing literature fails to effectively explain how the economy works since it assumes that all savings have a positive impact on the economy. Therefore, the savings are not all the same. Pending on the fact that there are enforcement savings then should be considered that they have a positive effect on the economy. On the other hand, the savings that do not come back to the economy should be considered to decrease the quantity of money in an economy (Challoumis, 2021f, 2022a). Therefore, the escapes savings are saved not to the country's economy, but to an external economic system. Thus, in the case of the enforcement savings, there is no decline in the quantity of money in an economy. But, in the case of escape savings, the economy is harmed, as becomes weaker, because of the lack and the decline of money quantity (Challoumis, 2020a, 2021h, 2022a). The result would be for the banking system to borrow more money to recover the lack of money because the money is saved in an external banking system.

This economic situation has resulted in this market consumption and investment being at the minimum level. Consumption is at a lower level when the escaped savings are at maximum level and therefore the enforcement savings are on their minimum level. Then the appropriate tax rate is required for the appropriate public policy (Cornelsen & Smith, 2018; Kominers et al., 2017; Limberg, 2020; Marengo et al., 2017; Martin & Freeland, 2021; Rashid et al., 2020; Siegmeier et al., 2018). Through the tax policy could be fixed the weakness of the economy, because of the increased escape savings. The fixed length principle serves the public policy with the lower taxation of uncontrolled transactions and the higher taxation of controlled transactions. The international companies which substitute the economic activities of the local and smaller companies usually because of the super profits can't consume and invest in the local market and banking system. In that way is plausible to avoid the lack of enforcement savings. The contracts and the agreements between the participants of control transactions are those that determine the allocation of profits and losses (Challoumis, 2018a, 2021b, 2021d, 2021c, 2021a, 2021g, 2021f, 2021e, 2022b, 2023a, 2023c, 2023b). To the agreements should be mentioned the changes in the contracts. This is the reason why the tax authorities should make

periodic inspections. The periodic specification of contracts is important for comparability analysis. These periodic inspections of the companies that participate in controlled transactions are crucial for the arm's length principle (Baker et al., 2020; Lucchese & Pianta, 2020; OECD, 2020; Ortun et al., 2017; Paes-Sousa et al., 2019; Sikka, 2018; TUTER, 2020). Then, the determination of the cost sharing depends on the periodic check of companies that are tested parties.

The scope of the companies of controlled transactions is to face the issues that are connected with the taxation of their activities. Therefore, the requirements for the companies of controlled transactions with the tax authorities should be in the range of the arm's length principle (Androniceanu et al., 2019; Bartels, 2005; Campos, 2015; Erickson, 2016; Hagensars et al., 2017; Khan & Liu, 2019; Trischler & Charles, 2019). Thereupon, the appropriate agreement of the companies of controlled transactions is that which permits them the maximization of their profits in tax environments with low tax rates, and the maximization of costs in economic environments with high tax rates (Anderson et al., 2020; Bergquist et al., 2020; Deng & Li, 2011; Koethenbuerger, 2011; Snow, 1988; Stern, 2015).

METHODOLOGY

The tax revenues correspond to the savings that the companies could have if the taxes were avoided. The way that these savings are administrated is different from case to case. Then the benefits of the companies could be managed in a completely different way, as could be saved or taxed (Challoumis, 2018b, 2019). The theory of the cycle of money shows when the savings robust the economy and when the taxes robust the economy. This determination must be a separation of savings into the non-returned savings (or escaped savings) and the returned savings (or enforcement savings). For the scope of this analysis below are demonstrated the equations which are:

$$\alpha = \alpha_s + \alpha_t = \frac{1}{v} + \alpha_t \quad (7)$$

$$x_m = m - a \quad (8)$$

$$m = \mu + \alpha_p \quad (9)$$

$$\mu = \sum_{i=0}^n \mu_i \quad (10)$$

$$\alpha_p = \sum_{j=0}^m \alpha_{pj} \quad (11)$$

$$c_m = \frac{dx_m}{dm} \quad (12)$$

$$c_\alpha = \frac{dx_m}{da} \quad (13)$$

$$c_y = c_m - c_\alpha \quad (14)$$

The variable of α symbolizes the case of the escaped savings. This means that there are savings that are not returned to the economy or come back after a

long-term period. The variable of α_s symbolizes the case that there are escaped savings that come from transfer pricing activities. The variable of α_t it symbolizes the case that there are escaped savings not from transfer pricing activities but from any other commercial activity. For instance, α_t could refer to the commercial activities that come from uncontrolled transactions. The variable of m symbolizes the financial liquidity in an economy. The variable of μ symbolizes the consumption in an economy. The variable of α_p symbolizes the enforcement savings, which come from the citizens and small and medium-sized enterprises. The variable of x_m symbolizes the condition of financial liquidity in an economy. The variable of c_m symbolizes the velocity of financial liquidity increases or decreases. The variable of c_α symbolizes the velocity of escaped savings. Therefore, the variable of c_y symbolizes the term of the cycle of money (Challoumis, 2021h, 2022a). Thereupon, the cycle of money shows the level of the dynamic of an economy and its robustness.

As a result, it is concluded that the money cycle grows when there is a tax system, such as the case of the fixed length principle, which allows for low taxation of uncontrolled transactions and higher taxation of controlled transactions. It should be noted that as uncontrolled transactions are considered, the same occurs in the cases of citizens and small and medium-sized businesses' financial liquidity. The following scheme depicts the prior analysis:

Figure 1: (a) Cycle of money (b) Worst case of cycle of money

Fig. 1 (a) shows the case of the escaping savings and the enforcement savings. Then, there is a connection between the higher tax policy for controlled transactions and the lower tax policy for uncontrolled transactions which is supported by the fixed length principle. In the model of the cycle of money without the enforcement savings [Fig. 1(b)] There is the worst hypothetical case where lost savings happen in the market. Therefore, in the second scheme, there is an economy that indicates a low economic dynamic environment.

DISCUSSION

As CM theory suggests, when booster savings are at a low level, then the money cycle is at a low level, which means that this economy is structurally bad. If booster savings are low, it means that structurally this economy is in trouble, because large corporations replace smaller ones, resulting in low dispersion and reuse of money. For the mathematical approach to the cycle of money:

$$m \approx \mu \tag{15}$$

$$\mu > \alpha_t > \alpha_s > 0 \tag{16}$$

Thus, it is obvious that the case of α_s omitted. After those clarifications applying the Q.E. method:

Factors	Values
α_s	0.6
α_t	0.7
μ	0.9

Table: Compiling coefficients

The generator of this procedure used the coefficients which appeared in the previous table. Therefore, the factors have an upper limit of 1, and a lower limit of 0, but s and \tilde{s} are plausible to receive values greater than one as their mathematical structure allows this. After 461 iterations the following diagrams:

Figure 2: (a) Three-dimensional representation of the cycle of money without the enforcement savings (b) Cycle of money without the enforcement savings

Fig. 2(a) illustrates the case of the three-dimensional representation of the cycle of money without escaping savings. Then, it is determined from that diagram that c_y and the c_m have very weak positive values, and c_α has its maximum effect, because the impact of the negative results is at a higher level. Therefore, it is obtained from diagram (a) of Fig.2 that there is an economy that suffers from an anemic increase in its economic dynamic behavior. The same conclusion comes from the diagram (b) of Fig. 2. Then is extracted the conclusion that the fixed length principle is important for an economy, as faces

those issues. Additionally, there is one more conclusion, which is about the fact that the worst economy has a physical positive orientation. Therefore, any economy that exists no matter its condition has a physical positive orientation. Then it is applied an econometric analysis with the Q.E. method:

Figure 3: Econometric analysis of the cycle of money without enforcement savings

Fig. 3 reveals that the needed variables of the model are stable, as the residuals do not have any important deviation from the expected values. Then the results of the E.Q.E. (Econometric Quantification of Everything) method are consistent with the residuals of the model, showing that the model is stable.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From this paper, it is obvious that when booster savings are at a low level, then a problem arises in the economy because both the diffusion, dispersion, and reuse of money are at a low level. The solution that emerges from CM's equations is the application of the FLP (Fix Length Principle), i.e. a distinct tax policy for large companies or companies that generally engage in controlled transactions, thus substituting smaller companies, thus reducing the quantity and functionality of money, while destroying the structure of the economy. This theory shows that the lack of enforcement savings leads to low consumption and the absence of investments. Then, taxation in combination with consumption, investments, and savings shows the way that public policy should act. The lack of enforcement savings destroys the economy. However, it

is clarified that in the worst case, there is a physical minimum level of positive economic dynamic behavior in any economy.

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